

Youth-Led Green Technological Innovations: Agents of Change towards Sustainability - An Indian Perspective

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Abstract

The twenty-first century is witnessing an unprecedented urgency to address environmental challenges, with the looming specter of climate change threatening the very foundation of our existence. Amidst this crisis, youth have emerged as potent change agents, driving innovative solutions in the realm of green technology. This abstract explores the pivotal role of youth in spearheading transformative change towards a sustainable future.

This research paper explores the pivotal role of youth as change agents in advancing green technology for sustainable development. In the context of escalating environmental challenges, youth empowerment and engagement are critical for driving transformative solutions. Through a comprehensive review of literature and case studies, this paper examines various aspects of youth involvement in the green technology sector, including innovation, entrepreneurship, collaborative networks, policy influence, behavioral change, and long-term impact.

Drawing upon empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks, it elucidates the mechanisms through which youth-led initiatives contribute to environmental sustainability and societal change. The paper also discusses the implications for research, policy, and practice in harnessing the potential of youth as drivers of innovation and sustainability. Ultimately, it underscores the importance of recognising and supporting youth as key stakeholders in shaping a more resilient and environmentally conscious future.

Keywords: *empowerment and engagement, environmental challenges, green technology, sustainable development, youth-led innovations*